

Intrinsic sorption potential of magnesium-aluminosilicate gel for Co^{2+} ions

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Cobalt sorption capacity of the hydrothermal gel close to mica mineral 'phlogopite' [$\text{Na/KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{OH}_2$] has been investigated at room temperature. The title gel has been synthesised by hydrothermal route at 160° . The cobalt selectivity of the gel has been studied in presence of 500–1000 times concentrated competing cations, viz. Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} . The cobalt uptake capacity has been reported as selectivity coefficient (K_d) and milliequivalent (Meq) of cobalt/100 g of the exchanger.

Synthetic fluorine micas have assumed importance in the literature of crystal chemistry as many of these substances are now commercial products. They find various applications in analytical chemistry such as detection and estimation of metal ions¹ as impregnants on papers and glass plates, in planar chromatography² and as adsorbents for pesticides³. The inorganic ion exchangers in contrast to their organic counterparts, exhibit remarkable potential as cobalt sorber. Mixed oxides of groups IV and V elements, cements, glasses, clay minerals, zeolites and mica group of minerals exhibit interesting ion exchange properties with respect to various alkali metals and transition metals^{4,5}. High chemical stability and selectivity for a particular ion is needed for the better utility of a material in separation science⁶. The object of this study is to evaluate the potential of the title compound for cobalt removal from mixed cationic solutions of liquid effluents. Here we report the data on cobalt sorption onto hydrothermally synthesised gel.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis for Mg, Al and Si shows that hydrothermal product is close to hydroxyphlogopite gel [$\text{Na/KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{OH}_2$]. The analyses are in good agreement with the theoretical values (in parenthesis) : Mg, 16.88 (17.14); K, 8.72 (9.28); Al, 6.98% (6.40%)⁷. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of the sample shows the maximum intensity at 16.86 Å ($2\theta = 5.23$). The other prominent peaks are observed at $d = 9.26$ and 1.53 Å. The X-ray pattern resembles that of the disordered potassium fluorophlogopite which may be gradually ordered to 1M type⁴. Table 1 shows the data on selective uptake by hydrothermal phase from mixed cationic solutions in the presence of 1000 times concentrated alkali and alkaline earth cations. The blocking effect in the uptake of Co^{2+} by the competing cations follows the sequence : $\text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Sr}^{2+}$. In case of larger cations like K^+ and Ba^{2+} , the removal of Co^{2+} is 29.5 and 15% respectively with 0.0005

$N \text{Co}^{2+}$, whereas in the presence of smaller cations like Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} the selectivity is 40, 28 and 25% respectively. The high selectivity of the gel is significantly retained in pure solutions of cobalt. It was also observed that the selectivity of the different cations decreases with increasing concentration of cobalt from 0.0001 to 0.0005 $N \text{Co}^{2+}$. The selectivity data indicate that less hydrated Co^{2+} ions are preferentially taken up over highly hydrated cations like Na^+ , K^+ and Mg^{2+} . Thus, the gel can be effectively used for the separation of cobalt from these cations even in the presence of 1000 times concentrated competing cations. Partial recovery (56%) of cobalt is possible when the gel is subjected to dil. acid (0.1 N) HCl for 24 h. Quantification of data on reverse exchange and the effect of di- and trivalent transition metal cations on cobalt sorption is under investigation. However, preliminary experiments show that the gel may be reused after recovery of cobalt.

Table 1. Selective sorption of Co^{2+} onto sodium phlogopite gel in presence of strong solution of competing cations*

Ion pair	Initial Co^{2+} mg dm^{-3}	ΔCo^{2+} mg dm^{-3}	I.S.C. meq/100 g	K_d ml g^{-1}	%Co removal
0.0001 $N \text{Co}^{2+}$ + 0.1 $N \text{M}^{n+}$:					
Co + Na	88.4	81.2	1376.27	11277.78	91.85
Co + K	96.6	70.2	1189.83	2659.09	72.67
Co + Ca	99.9	71.5	1211.86	2517.61	71.78
Co + Ba	110.1	77.9	1320.34	2415.50	70.72
Co + Sr	124.0	71.7	1215.25	1370.94	57.87
0.0005 $N \text{Co}^{2+}$ + 0.1 $N \text{M}^{n+}$:					
Co + Na	24.0	9.6	162.71	666.66	40.0
Co + K	24.4	7.2	122.03	428.57	29.5
Co + Ca	26.4	7.5	127.12	396.83	28.4
Co + Mg	21.6	5.4	91.50	333.33	25.0
Co + Ba	31.2	4.8	81.30	181.82	15.3
Co + Sr	36.0	14.4	244.07	666.67	40.0

* Δ = Initial Co^{2+} concn. – final Co^{2+} concn.

K_d (distribution coefficient) = $\left(\frac{C_0}{C_e} - 1\right) \times A/M$: C_0 = initial concn. of Co^{2+} , C_e = final concn. of Co^{2+} , A = vol. of soln. (ml), M = mass of the exch. (g).

D_f = decontamination factor = $\frac{\text{initial Co concn.}}{\text{final Co concn.}}$

% Co removal = $\Delta \times 100/\text{initial Co concn.}$

I.S.C. = Ion sorption capacity.

Table 2 shows that with increase in concentration of Na^+ from 0.2 to 2 N the capacity of Co^{2+} uptake decreases. The comparative volume study of %Co removal shows that with increase in volume of eluent from 10 to 25 ml the Co^{2+} uptake decreases from 88.2 to 64% respectively, for 0.2 N sodium. The K_d value decreases linearly from 3200 to 800 for 10 ml of eluent and it also decreases from 1779 to 151 for 25 ml of eluent. The mass balance data is shown in Table 3. A maximum of 335.6 meq/100 g of Co^{2+} uptake has been observed. Thus, the gel can be effectively used for separation of cobalt from a mixture of cations. Therefore, it could be a potential additive for solidification and immobilisation of cobalt in industrial and radioactive waste effluents⁸.

Table 2. Selective uptake of Co^{2+} onto sodium phlogopite gel in presence of competing Na^+ cation

Normality of soln. = 0.0001 N Co^{2+} + 0.2 to 2 N Na^+ , wt. of exch. = 25 mg, equilibration time = 24 h

Na^+ N	Initial Co^{2+} mg dm ⁻³	Final Co^{2+} mg dm ⁻³	Δ	D_f	% Co removal	K_d ml g ⁻¹
Vol. of soln. = 10 ml :						
0.2	7.2	0.8	6.4	9.00	88.88	3200.00
0.4	8.8	1.2	7.6	7.30	86.36	2533.33
0.6	8.8	1.4	7.4	6.29	84.09	2114.29
0.8	8.6	1.6	7.0	5.38	81.40	1750.00
1.0	9.0	1.8	7.2	5.00	80.00	1600.00
1.2	9.0	2.4	6.6	3.75	73.33	1100.00
1.4	8.6	2.4	6.2	3.58	72.09	1033.33
1.6	8.6	2.6	6.0	3.31	69.77	923.08
1.8	9.0	2.8	6.2	3.21	68.89	885.71
2.0	9.0	3.0	6.0	3.00	66.66	800.00
Vol. of soln. = 25 ml :						
0.2	16.0	5.9	10.5	2.77	64.02	1711.86
0.4	17.6	7.2	10.4	2.44	59.09	1444.44
0.6	12.8	6.6	6.20	1.93	48.43	939.39
0.8	13.6	7.6	6.00	1.78	44.11	789.47
1.0	10.4	6.0	4.40	1.73	42.30	733.33
1.2	6.0	4.2	1.80	1.42	30.00	428.57
1.4	8.0	6.0	2.00	1.33	25.00	333.33
1.6	7.6	6.0	1.60	1.26	21.05	266.66
1.8	6.4	5.2	1.20	1.23	18.75	230.76
2.0	7.6	6.6	1.00	1.15	13.15	151.51

Experimental

Sodium/potassium hydroxyphlogopite gel [$\text{Na/KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{OH}_2$] is close to the composition of fluorine mica mineral [$\text{Na/KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{F}_2$]. The gel was synthesised by the following procedure. Metal ions Na/K, Mg, Si, Al along with OH ions were taken in molar ratios 1 : 3 : 3 : 1 : 2 respectively, to give a homogenous paste in double-distilled decarbonated water (10 ml). Aqueous solution of $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, K_2SiO_3 , $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ and NaOH in stoichiometric ratio was used as starting material. On mixing the aqueous solutions a white glassy mass separated out. The thick precipitate after thorough homogenation was then transferred to a teflon-lined stainless steel pressure vessel. Additional amount of water was added to keep the

total solid-water ratio equal to 1 : 5. The mixture was autoclaved in pressure bomb and kept in an oven (200°) for 72 h. After hydrothermal treatment the contents were filtered, washed with distilled water and dried in an oven (120°). The chemical composition of the product was verified by elemental analysis using atomic absorption/flame emission spectrophotometry following the borate fusion method for silicate minerals⁹. The XRD pattern of the gel was recorded on a computer interfaced PW-1820 diffractometer system using Ni filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation.

Table 3. Mass balance data of Co^{2+} exchange onto sodium hydroxyphlogopite gel

Wt. of exch. = 25 mg, vol. of soln. = 10 ml, equilibration time = 24 h

Initial Co^{2+} mg/100 ml	Co sorbed mg/100 ml	Co in solid meq/100 g
11.17	05.07	085.93
22.34	06.10	103.38
33.51	10.78	172.20
44.68	11.47	194.41
55.85	12.88	218.30
59.14	13.66	231.52
64.30	14.10	238.98
73.52	15.01	254.40
82.71	15.07	222.46
91.90	19.80	335.59

The gel (100 mg) was equilibrated with mixed solution (10 ml) containing 5×10^{-4} / 1×10^{-4} N cobalt and 0.1 N of each of the competing cations, viz. Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} separately. Sorption studies were also carried out separately on pure cobalt solution ranging from 100–1000 mg dm⁻³.

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References

1. K. G. Varshney, S. Rani, S. Anwar and U. Sharma, *Anal. Lett.*, 1985, **18**, 2033.
2. K. G. Varshney, A. A. Khan, S. M. Maheshwari and U. Gupta, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1992, **65**, 2773; K. G. Varshney, A. Ali and M. S. Siddiqui, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India, Sect. A*, 1993, **63**, 495.
3. K. G. Varshney, A. A. Khan, S. M. Maheshwari and U. Gupta, *Colloids Surf.*, 1993, **69**, 265.
4. T. Noda and R. Roy, *Am. Mineralogist*, 1956, **41**, 929.
5. R. Tomar and O. P. Shrivastava, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 952; S. Komarneni and D. M. Roy, *Science*, 1983, **221**, 647; US Pat. 4537710/1985; Clearfield and J. M. Kalinis, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 1933; J. L. Nelson and B. W. Mercer, US Atomic Energy Commission, Hanford, Washington Report Doc. No. HW-76449, p. 31; O. P. Shrivastava, S. Komarneni and P. Malla, *Mat.*

- Res. Bull.*, 1991, **26**, 357; O. P. Shrivastava, P. K. Wattal and T. Verma, *J. Adv. Cement Based Mat.*, 1995, **2**, 80; O. P. Shrivastava and T. Verma, *J. Adv. Cement Based Mat.*, 1995, **2**, 119.
6. B. Pandit and U. Chudasama, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **5**, 77.
 7. O. P. Shrivastava, R. Tomar and R. Shrivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 922.
 8. O. P. Shrivastava, T. Verma and R. Shrivastava, "Cation Exchange Applications of Synthetic Silicate Minerals for Immobilisation and Solidification of Simulated Nuclear Waste in Cement Matrix", DAE Project Report No. 38/3/91-G, 1994.
 9. C. O. Inagmells, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **52**, 323.